

THE FOOL IN AFRICA: A FEMINIST READING OF EDDIE MURPHY'S COMING TO AMERICA

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Abstract

Motion pictures are works and they are intended to be appreciated as art. As a result, movies are frequently referred to as entertainment, despite the fact that they contain ideologies that the director intends for the audience to absorb either directly or indirectly. Based on this context, this essay uses Lois Tyson's concept of feminism which holds that any work that denigrates women or portrays them as inferior beings is patriarchal to analyze Eddie Murphy's Coming to America. Imani, Akeem's "carefully selected African bride," is portrayed in the movie as the ideal of an African woman. Imani is portrayed as a woman who has no independent thought and simply obeys her king's orders like a dog should. This by extension shows there are no women in Africa who are fit to rule as queens. This essay comes to the conclusion that patriarchy and segregation are combined in the representation of African women, with this time the bias being locational rather than racial. Such messages should not be supported in any form, whether it be in writing, painting, drama, or film, because they are untrue.

Introduction

A fool is defined by the Cambridge Dictionary as someone who acts rashly without thinking. The King James dictionary gives the impression of what this paper will attempt to define as a fool. In layman's terms, a fool is a person who exhibits some intellectual weakness but is not an idiot; a person who behaves absurdly; a person who does not use reason; a person who follows a path against the advice of wisdom. After watching Eddie Murphy's timeless classic

Coming to America, I got this impression. The best choice for Prince Akeem (Eddie Murphy) as a queen in the movie is Imani Izzi, played by Vanessa Bell. Imani is portrayed as a woman who is incapable of making wise decisions; in the movie, she stands in for all African women. The question that arises is: Is the African woman really a fool or is she a Queen deserving of a King? This paper was inspired by the search for this solution, which is emphasized in the movie *Coming to America*. However, before we analyze the movie *Coming to America*, it is crucial that we understand what is film and how it communicates meaning David Cook (1997) opines that.

The illusion of motion pictures is based on the optical phenomena known as persistence of vision and the phi phenomenon. The first of these causes the brain to retain images cast upon the retina of the eye for a fraction of a second beyond their disappearance from the field of sight, while the latter creates apparent movement between images when they succeed one another rapidly. Together these phenomena permit the succession of still frames on a motion-picture film strip to represent continuous movement when projected at the proper speed (traditionally 16 frames per second for silent films and 24 frames per second for sound films) (1).

With this definition, a movie/film may be easily understood as a collection of still images that are ordered in a particular command and are projected onto a screen. With the aid of a machine or technology, these still images are projected to the audience at a rate of 16 or 24 frames per second. These still images are made to move over light. Then, the brain analyzes these images to create a narrative from them. Because of this, it is occasionally referred to as a motion picture, or simply as a picture in motion. Tracing its history, the concept of the photograph gave birth to the motion picture which is popularly called film or cinema. According to Brian Marley (2011),

The history of film cannot be credited to one individual as an oversimplification of any history often tries to do. Each inventor added to the progress of other inventors, culminating in progress for the entire art and industry. Often masked in mystery and fable, the beginnings of film and the silent era of motion pictures are usually marked by a stigma of crudeness and naiveté, both on the audience's and filmmakers' parts. However, with the landmark depiction of a train hurtling toward and past the camera, the Lumière Brothers' 1895 picture “La Sortie de l'Usine Lumière à Lyon” (“Workers Leaving the Lumière Factory”), was only one of a series of simultaneous artistic and technological breakthroughs that began to culminate at the end of the nineteenth century (1).

The motion picture is a product of different technological breakthroughs across Europe and America, each scientist improving on the other's discovery. The advancement on pre-existing technology in the late 19th century gave birth to the first camera that could capture the movement of bodies/objects more than sixteen times per-second.

The ability of a camera to take multiple shots per second, according to Marley, gave birth to movies. He further adds that:

The movie industry was born in these years (late nineteenth century) but the ideas of what the industry could and would become had not yet been completely conceived. Films were still a novelty and an experiment. However, with the advent of the now available Cinematography and Vitascope, theaters

opened across Europe and the US, and filmmakers began to create new forms of what would soon be understood to be not only a new form of art but a profitable one” (8).

This new form of art known as the motion picture or film, has grown to be a popular form of entertainment in the twentieth and twenty first centuries. There have been different ways of calling the filmic art; it is sometimes known as the edutainment art and infotainment art, because it plays a dual function: to entertain and to educate, or inform and also educate. According to Marley, film or motion picture is art. As art, it is meant to be appreciated. The concept and process of appreciating a literal text can equally be applicable to a film. Totawad N. Ramrao (2016) justifies this as he compares film and literature:

Film and literature are two different things with a similar goal to create sublimity in human imagination and understanding. Both film and literature work hand in hand to boost the progress of human civilization. And they are the [sic] complimentary in nature and one is no substitute to the other, like letters and sounds in human communication. Film and literature inspire and enrich each others. They also ennoble human mind through action, images, words and replicating life of human beings (2).

The same functions and attributes accrued to Literature are also visible in film and with this background, it is important not to just see a film as a tool for just entertainment but a vehicle to convey thought, belief, ideas and also theories. This is because the film is used to educate, inform, inspire and also preserve information just like any literary work we come across.

According to Allwell Onukaogu, Onyekwere Okpara and Ezechi Onyerionwu (2011) in their book *Literary Appreciation A Demonstrative Reader*, the film is

one of the most recent of the art form and its major strength is its accessibility and the power of closeness to life. According to them, “film has been considered in many quarters as the most effective of all the art forms” (64). They further illustrate that the range and reach of film is unapparelled, film unlike literature gives us moving images directly, giving it an edge over painting and photography.

The nexus between literary theories adopted as lenses to interrogate audio-visual materials like film is explained by Mohammad Khosravi Shakib (2013), that there are two major types of Intertextuality, which are *ekphrasis* and *iconotext*. Ekphrasis was defined by Tom Mitchel, Grant Scott and James Hefferman as "the verbal representation of visual representation" while David Carrier sees it as a "verbal re-creations of visual artwork" concept of intertextuality. He further highlights the theories by Pluto, Aristotle and Roman theorist which he explains as a theory of imitation. He explains thus:

According to Roman theorists, imitation presupposes reference to a pre-existent reality which is concrete as well as textual... imitation is not repetition; it is a highlighting in which by reading and writing, the translator declares his/herself, while also engaging in a process of self-alienation... It is neither a copy nor an original. (2)

This essay focuses on the literary material utilized in the movie, including the language and the translator's approach to turning written content into visual imagery. Due to this portrayal, the article is inspired to use semiotics to analyze the words the actors are using and how they are using them. Given this context, it is not unreasonable to assert that Eddie Murphy's *Coming to America* inspires and informs viewers in equal measure while also educating them. Determining the information the film is conveying to its audience is crucial for this reason. In order to highlight how the African woman has been portrayed to the world since the late 1980s when the movie was released, we will analyze the movie using feminist lenses as a guide.

Feminism is not a recent development; it has existed for a long time. There are numerous books and academic articles that discuss feminism. From the religious feminists of biblical times to the radical feminists of the twenty-first century, they all share and have the same concerns over patriarchy. By definition, patriarchy is "sexist," which means it encourages the idea that women are biologically inferior to men and therefore, inherently inferior to them. As Lois Tyson explains in *Critical Theory Today: A User-Friendly Guide*:

Feminists don't deny the biological difference between men and women; in fact many feminists celebrate those differences. But they don't agree that such differences like size, shape, and body chemistry make men naturally superior to women; for example more intelligent, more logical more courageous, or better leaders (84).

According to Tyson, any work that supports these aforementioned views is patriarchal and places the woman as an inferior being. This inferiority is not based on biology but culturally produced or masterminded to subjugate the woman. For Tyson, "patriarchy continually exerts forces that undermine women's self-confidence and assertiveness, then points to the absence of these qualities as proof that women are naturally, and therefore correctly, self-effacing and submissive. (85)

This paper utilizes the feminist ideology that Tyson succinctly outlined in his analysis of *Coming to America* because it is essential for us to be able to recognize when and how patriarchal ideology operates in order to be able to resist it in our thoughts, daily lives, and society at large. Knowing when a piece of art—be it a painting, a book, a movie, etc.—depicts patriarchal ideology allows one to criticize it or draw attention to it so that it can be criticized. Based on Lois Tyson:

Because feminist issues range so widely across cultural, social political, and psychological categories, feminist literary criticism is wide ranging too. Whatever kind of analysis is undertaken, however, the ultimate goal of feminist criticism is to increase our understanding of women's experience, both in the past and present, and promote our appreciation of women's value in the world (100-1).

This paper looks at how women are portrayed, particularly with the issue of a woman's location and how that makes her superior to another woman in another location, as it is portrayed in the movie *Coming to America*. This criticism is significant because, in contrast to the majority of patriarchal works, the oppression or discrimination here is location-based rather than based on gender inequality as in mainstream feminism or limited to skin color as enunciated in Alice Walker's womanism. As implied in the movie, *Coming to America*, women (white or black) living in America happen to be better than women (white or black) living in Africa. This paper adopts Tyson's feminist crux of increasing understanding of women and their experiences as portrayed in the film *Coming to America*. This feminist feature is examined and explained through two throbs of audio-visual analysis: the language use and the semiotic representation (pictures) in the movie.

The film's plot revolves around Zamunda, the Prince of an African Monarch, who is set to wed Imani Izzi on his 21st birthday. After seeing her personality during their first encounter, he decides to travel New York for forty days with his father's approval. Prince Akeem has other ideas than what his father thinks he wants to do—sow his royal oaths. He leaves behind his comfortable privileges and marries an American woman. Prince Akeem (not the more Arab "Hakeem") hides his royal heritage in order to more successfully assimilate into American society and to find a woman who will value him for qualities other than wealth and status.

According to Zeke (2010), “this plot relies heavily on old story pieces of wealth, honesty and disguise. But it stands out from the Hollywood crowd by virtue of the contemporary context in which it couches those elements. The film depicts the main character's homeland, Zamunda, as a place where members of the royal family lead luxurious lives, so wholly ensconced by wealth and aristocratic tradition that ordinary living seems unimaginable.” Even though there is no place in Africa by the name “Zamunda” in the movie, it is clearly depicted as a place in Africa, and Akeem is nicknamed Kunta Kinte, the African boy in James Harley's *Roots*. In Zeke's review of the film, he further adds that:

While *Coming to America* could have centered around a European monarchy... It challenges our stereotypes of where wealth and high education can exist. While many Americans conceive of Africa as a uniformly destitute region whose cultures have never reached the grand accomplishments of their European counterparts, this comedy reminds us that great forms of civilization have and do exist in what we still too often consider the “dark continent”... Perhaps if other popular movies were as careful as *Coming to America* in depicting cultural dynamics between the US and Africa, not so many harmful stereotypes would persist (2-3).

Zeke's view of the movie was good and wished other well-known films were as cautious as *Coming to America*. This essay adopts a different stance from Zeke's point of view and not only that, but also how the entire movie portrays the African lady through selected film clips and speech, particularly the way the language is used to represent the African woman.

Before the first ten minutes of the film, the subject matter is obvious, “a wife/Queen” for the Prince.

- Akeem: It is not just that, it is everything. The cooking, the pampering, the dressing, the bathing...Actually, I rather enjoy the bathing, but I'd like to cook for myself, dress myself, wipe my own backside. And why can't I find my own wife?
- King: Aha! So that's it? We've gone through a lot of trouble to select for you a very fine wife. Since she was born, she was taught to walk, speak and think as a queen. (8:44-9:11 min)

This dialogue between the king and his troubled son, Akeem, brings to bare the trajectory of the film. The opening five minutes of the film introduces us to the prince of Zamunda, Akeem, an over pampered, charming and lazy character who is not allowed to bathe himself. In this paper, we will focus on how African women are portrayed rather than Akeem's machismo. Akeem could also be used as a study subject in the future.

In the movie, there is a juxtaposition of two types of women - the women living in Africa and the women living in America. Through the above dialogue between the King and his son, the first type of woman, the woman in Africa is introduced by the king; carefully selected from birth, taught, and nurtured to be a wife and queen; in terms of how to walk, talk and her aura. The second category of women happen to be the ones Akeem needs, an ideal, independent and opinionated woman. He foregrounds his thoughts and reason thus:

- Semmi: So you can have a woman who will obey your every command, but you'd rather have a woman who has an opinion?
- Akeem: Only dogs are to obey. If you love your wife, you'll value her opinion.
- Semmi: Hippopotamus shit! You're the heir to the throne of Zamunda. Your wife need only have a pretty face, firm backside and big breasts.

- Akeem: So you would share your bed, and your fortune, with a beautiful fool?
- Semmi: That's the way it's always been with men of power. It's tradition. (11:11-12:06min)

The contention of the kind of woman is being discussed between Prince Akeem, his friend and valet, Semmi and they both make strong statements about the woman. Semmi brings to mind two different kinds of women. The first is the woman conditioned by a patriarchal society to obey the command of men, and the second is the liberated woman who has an opinion of her own. Akeem gives an answer, “only dogs are to obey”, then he drives home his point when he asks if Semmi will share his bed and wealth with a “beautiful fool”.

This dialogue introduces and raises the interest of the audience to see who actually will be presented to Akeem as a wife. Indeed, when it was time, her entrance was grand and befitting of a queen, her appearance was breathtaking, but of her intellect, the following conversations give an insight:

- Imani: Am I not all you dreamed I would be?
- Akeem: You're fine. Beautiful. But if we're going to be married, we should talk and get to know each other.
- Imani: Ever since I was born, I have been trained to serve you.
- Akeem: I know, but I'd like to know about you. What do you like to do?
- Imani: Whatever you like.
- Akeem: What kind of music do you like?
- Imani: Whatever kind of music you like.
- Akeem: I know what I like, and you

know what I like, 'cause you were trained to know, but I would like to know what you like. Do you have a favourite food? Good! What is your favourite food?

Imani: Whatever food you like.

Akeem: This is impossible. I command you not to obey me.

Imani: No.

Akeem: Are you saying that no matter what I tell you to do, you will do?

Imani: Yes, your Highness.

Akeem: Anything I say, you'll do?

Imani: Yes, your Highness.

Akeem: Bark like a dog...A big dog...Hop on one leg. (18:17-19:35)

The above excerpts will serve as the language indices for our analysis, which will focus on how the language is utilized to describe the category of African women. Akeem begins with a description of a woman who has no independent thought, which presents a disparaging picture of African women from his choice of language. A woman who is raised to be her husband's servant and not a queen. Her response and subsequent behavior during and after the talk are funny. The woman in Africa is a joke, and it is unwise to pay heed to her thoughts, deeds, or demeanor.

The semiotic representation of this scene is equally worth the thought. When Akeem orders his queen to be, who was carefully selected from birth and tutored in the ways of royalty to bark like a dog, with no hesitation or question, like a dog, she obeyed, Akeem then looks at the camera (the viewer) (9:17-9:23min) in figure 1, 2 and 3

Fig 1

This is when Akeem came to the realization that Imani was and is programmed to obey him.

Fig. 2

This is when Imani starts to bark like a puppy, and Akeem looks into the camera and orders her to bark like a big dog.

Fig 3

Imani in her glory, barking like a big dog.

Fig. 4

In figure four above, he further degrades her to hop on one leg while barking like a dog

Fig 5

While Akeem stands as a taskmaster watching his dog follow him, Imani is behaving devoutly.

Though made humorous, the semiotic portrayal of this event is a slap on the African lady for the sake of this study. First off, he is confirming to the viewers what he had previously said to Semi by staring directly into the camera: "Only a dog obeys whatever he or she is instructed. The second is that we, as the audience, can concur with Akeem that the female in front of him, who is hopping on one leg and barking like a dog, portrays the African woman as indeed a dog and cannot be a queen. He didn't need to say anything; the way Akeem glances at the audience (the camera) before turning back to the girl speaks volumes only through the cinematic narratology.

This action by Akeem is a buildup from the scene he had with his father about who he wants to marry. According to the king, Imani was the best Africa could offer him and she is an excellent bride. And the excellence of Africa is a woman who doesn't have a voice of her own, no willpower, no voice but just an obedient servant, and in a simple metaphor, she is nothing but a dog who obeys the bidding of her master. This leads us to the second aspect of the spectrum: who is befitting enough for the prince, Akeem if Africa is not worth it? Where

will he get his Queen? Who will be the Queen? A lady befitting enough to tickle both the intellect and emotions of the Prince; a lady who will have an opinion of her own and equally challenge Akeem. Judging from what the King said earlier, “We've gone through a lot of trouble to select for you a very fine wife” summarizes the whole argument: “this is the best this land can offer”, and the best the land could offer was a woman who is not fit to be a queen but a dog. Then he finds out an alternative, a place where he can get a wife

Semmi: This trip is an excellent idea. 40 days of fornication.

Akeem: Semmi. I have something else in mind. I intend to find my bride.

Semmi: What is wrong with the one you have? Didn't you want to rip her clothes off?

Akeem: I want a woman who will arouse my intellect as well as my loins.

Semmi: Where would you find such a woman?

Akeem: In America. (22:17-22:40 min)

Semmi asked a profound question and Akeem gives him a conclusion, to explain further, they are no queens in Zamunda, the only place I can get a queen for my throne is in America. This can only be a portraiture of a colonial and a neocolonial mentality. Anything African is substandard and anything foreign is superior. But the crux of this paper is not postcolonialism but feminism, if not it would have been an interesting trajectory.

The title of the movie, *Coming to America*, refers to the action of traveling to America. Let's first take a closer look at Lisa, the Queen he ultimately encountered in America. It's interesting to note that they first met at a black awareness pageant, where she was one of the organizers rather than a contender. Even before she started speaking, Akeem was drawn to her, and by the time she finished, he had already fallen in love with her. What do you think drew him to her? Imani and Lisa both shared the trait of "beauty" back in those days in Africa not self-opinion. In the club, he met different girls who had

opinions of their own and striking character, an example is Peaches:

Girl in Blue: I want to work in videos, but I want to be my own star in the video, because I want to be a pop singer, a rock singer, and write my own songs. And then I'm going to try an actress, 'cause people tell me I'm a natural. Then I'm going to write and direct my own stories, produce the movies... (35:31- 36:10)

The Girl in Blue, who does not actually have a name, fits Akeem's stereotype of a woman, which is ironic in this moment. She is quite opinionated and had her own ideas. The D.Js want to touch her breast, but she is not interested because she has specific objectives that she is determined to achieve. But instead of falling in love with her, Akeem dozes off during her speech. In fact, this goes against everything Akeem values in a woman. According to the plot, Akeem falls in love with Lisa, who never expressed an opinion but charmed him in the same way Imani did in *Zamunda*.

Coming to America's depiction of how gender and race intertwine when viewed through a feminist lens makes the character Cholly from Toni Morrison's *The Bluest Eye* come to mind. Lois Tyson asserts that:

for Cholly's hatred of Darlene is the direct result of the Black youngster's powerlessness in the face of the white hunters' racism and the importance of sisterhood to women's survival becomes especially acute when the women are victims of the combined forces of sexism and racism (99).

The importance of sisterhood is key to women survival when they are faced with the same problem, and feminism is not just a movement for the

Americans, but a global call. That is to say, women in a particular geographical area should not be made to feel, look or presented as inferior to another group of women because they are sisters. The concept/idea of a geographical area having queens and the other not having women fit enough to be queens is what the film *Coming to America* is guilty of.

Let's look at the period when the movie was released; the production log indicates that it did so in January 1888. At that time, how did African women feel? Was she sufficiently portrayed in the movie? If yes, then the makers of the film are justified in their representation. We will first examine this from a literary standpoint before examining the political and social context of African women at that time in history.

There are many African authors who have achieved success in literature and who have also written about the African woman in their works. Mariama Ba (1929), Florence Nwanzuruahu Nkiru Nwapa (1931), Zulu Sofola (1935), Ama Ata Aidoo (1942), and Florence Onyebuchi "Buchi" Emecheta (1944) are only a few African women who achieved literary success before the premiere of the movie *Coming to America* in 1988. Not just in Africa, but also internationally renowned for having strong opinions and standing up to injustice. We have examples of African women who were similarly accomplished in their period but did not write. The following individuals were named by Msafropolitan in her article "African Female Icon that Shaped History": from 2010 Funmilayo Ransome Kuti, the woman activist; Yaa Asantewa, the commander in chief; Winnie Mandela, the first lady's spouse; Margaret Ekpo, the stylish feminist; Miriam Makeba, the mother of Africa; Queen Nzinga, the reformer; and Ruth Williams, to Lady Khama. These are just a few of the women who have made a difference in the world. All of these ladies left their mark by defending not just their rights but also women's rights in Africa before 1988.

With these few examples in mind, one would wonder what standard Eddie Murphy's *Coming to America* is using to evaluate the African woman in the movie. This is an unfair and too harsh way to portray any woman, or more specifically, a certain set of women that live in a specific location. Zeke (2010)

seems to be justifying the portrayal of the African woman in the movie by saying, "Perhaps if other popular movies were as careful as *Coming to America* in depicting cultural dynamics between the US and Africa, not so many harmful stereotypes would persist." Finally, what detrimental stereotype could possibly be worse than what was portrayed in the movie?

The question one should consider is, "Do we have women in Africa who are worthy of being queens?" This will help to further explain how the creators of *Coming to America* depicted the image of the African woman in the character of Imani, who serves as a microcosm of all African women and the fictional nation of Zamunda. This is not just a patriarchal mindset in its portrayal of Imani; it also combines segregation with patriarchy, except that this time the bias is based on place rather than race. Imani's presentation in the video makes the provocative claim that African women are not suitable to be queens. They provide further evidence to the contrary by introducing Aoleon, another African woman.

Akeem's mother, Aoleon, is a queen in every sense of the word. Rather than Imani, she ought to serve as a representation of what an African woman ought to be: bold, courageous, independent, and willing to challenge the king.

Queen: Jaffe, apologize to Mr.
McDowell.
King: I will not. The man is beneath
me, and so is his daughter.
Akeem: What did you tell her?
King: It is of no consequence. We shall
return to Zamunda at once.
Akeem: I will not leave without Lisa.
Queen: So you do care for her?
Akeem: Mother, I love her.
Queen: Then go after her.
King: Akeem! I forbid you.
Queen: Put a sock in it, Jaffe. The boy's in love
(1:39:30- 1:41:23)

With this dialogue, the queen is no pushover; she has equal right and power like her husband, the King. She further shows her strength when she talks with the King in the car:

King: You're still not speaking to me.
Queen: I only want our son to be happy.
King: And so do I. Aoleon, please. It is out of our hands. The girl told him no.
Queen: After the way you treated her, who could blame her?
King: Even if she said yes, they still couldn't marry. It's against the tradition.
Queen: Well, it is a stupid tradition.
King: Who am I to change it?
Queen: I thought you were the King.
(1:47:48- 1:48:16)

Because of this debate and how the film ended out, the queen was finally able to modify the tradition that the king had been striving to uphold. This shift can be attributed to Akeem's smile at the queen when he realized Lisa, not Imani, was the woman he was about to wed. This particular outcome demonstrates the power of the African woman and also validates the power of the pioneering African women who supported and triumphed in the fight for women's equality against patriarchal preconceptions. The image of the African woman that should be represented is Aoleon, not the one that was shown to us in the form of Imani, who had nothing but slavery to offer.

Conclusion

Despite the African woman's beauty and individuality, and despite the reality of her fortitude and will to live against the oppression of a patriarchal society, a 1988 film masterpiece decided to portray an African woman as having no independent thought. A woman who is raised to be a "yes sir" type of person, one who they themselves describe as a "fool" with no voice, and whose sole

purpose in life is to obey her spouse. This viewpoint runs counter to the actual situation. African women today are powerful, opinionated, and bold. The character of Aoleon Joffer (the Queen), who withstood the King, Akeem dreaded and, in the end, used her authority to persuade him to reverse an edict he had initially declared was impossible to carry out, is evidence that African women can be queens in real life. This demonstrates the resilience of African women rather than how Imani is portrayed.

Coming to America. Directed by John Landis, starring; Eddie Murphy, Paramount Pictures, 1988.

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